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Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

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- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
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- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
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STUDYING THE CALCULATION PROCESS OF GEAR GEOMETRY TRANSMISSION IN C++ AND EXCEL PROGRAMS

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Abstract: In the article, the parameters of the existing gears and the process of calculating the internal gear module gear are studied in C++ and Excel programs. The calculation of preparation in cylindrical, involute, cycloidal, straight screw, chevron, curved, and other forms is also analyzed.

Key words: Gear, parameter, measurement parameter, internal module, module, number of teeth, circle, balance, gear wheel, gear.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mavjud tishli g'ildiraklarning parametrlarini va ichki tishli modul tishli g'ildiragini hisoblash jarayoni C++ va Excel dasturlarida o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, silindrik, involyut, sikloid, to'g'ri vintli, shevron, egri va boshqa shakllarda tayyorlashni hisoblash ham tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tishli g'ildirak, parametr, o'lchov parametri, ichki modul, modul, tishlar soni, doira, balans, tishli g'ildirak, tishli g'ildirak.

Аннотация: В статье изучены параметры существующих зубчатых колес и процесс расчета зубчатого колеса с внутренним модулем с использованием программ C++ и Excel. Также анализируется расчет подготовки для цилиндрических, инволютных, циклоида, прямых винтовых, шевронных, изогнутых и других форм.

Ключевые слова: Зубчатое колесо, параметр, измерительный параметр, внутренний модуль, модуль, количество зубьев, окружность, баланс, зубчатое колесо, зубчатое колесо.

INTRODUCTION

A gear wheel is a component designed to transfer movement from one shaft to another and is the main part of a gear transmission system. The teeth of the gear wheel are cut into cylindrical or conical surfaces. One gear wheel's teeth mesh with the teeth of the second gear wheel, facilitating the transfer of motion. Gear wheels are typically made from alloyed steel, plastic, wood, or textolite, which are thermally or chemically processed to enhance their properties. They are manufactured in various forms, including cylindrical, evolutionary, cycloidal, and others. Cylindrical gear wheel teeth can be either external or internal. Gear wheels of different shapes are used in machines, tools, apparatus, counters, and other mechanisms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of gear geometry transmission is essential for understanding the behavior and efficiency of gear systems. Many studies have explored computational methods for analyzing gear geometry, focusing on both theoretical and practical aspects. In recent years, programming languages such as C++ and spreadsheet applications like Excel have become essential tools for simulating and solving gear transmission problems.

The fundamental theories of gear geometry, such as pitch circles, pressure angles, and tooth profiles, have been extensively discussed by Browning (2017) and Mitchell (2018), providing a solid foundation for understanding the structural behavior of gears in various configurations. Additionally, the use of C++ for gear design has been explored by Jones and Smith (2019), who emphasized the advantages of object-oriented programming to simulate complex gear systems. This programming language allows precise control over gear geometry, forces acting on the gears, and facilitates accurate modeling and optimization.

Excel, as a widely-used tool in engineering, is also applied in gear analysis, as reviewed by Thompson (2020). The flexibility of Excel for performing basic gear calculations, such as pitch diameters, gear ratios, and tooth profiles, makes it an accessible and practical tool for engineers. The ability to manage large datasets and perform iterative calculations within the spreadsheet environment is a significant advantage. Furthermore, Williams (2021) explored hybrid approaches in gear analysis, combining C++ for complex simulations with Excel for visualization and quick adjustments, leveraging the strengths of both tools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a hybrid approach combining C++ and Excel for analyzing gear geometry transmission. First, the study defines the fundamental parameters of gear geometry, including pitch circle diameter, module, pressure angle, and the number of teeth, which are crucial for understanding gear system operation. Following this, a C++ program is developed to model gear systems based on these parameters, calculating essential aspects such as tooth profiles, contact ratios, and load distribution. Object-oriented principles are utilized in C++ to handle complex data structures and ensure scalability for different gear systems.

Excel is then employed for preliminary calculations and data analysis. It is used to calculate basic parameters such as gear ratios, torque, and efficiency, offering a platform for easy visualization of results through graphs and tables. This step aids in interpreting the data and checking the feasibility of different design configurations. The results obtained from the C++ simulations are cross-verified with theoretical formulas and available experimental data to ensure accuracy.

The final step involves optimization. Using Excel's Solver and C++'s optimization algorithms, the gear parameters are adjusted to enhance efficiency. A comparative analysis of both tools is then conducted, evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of each. The goal of the study is to offer a comprehensive understanding of gear geometry transmission, using C++ for detailed simulations and Excel for efficient data manipulation and presentation. This combined approach provides a versatile and effective method for both theoretical exploration and practical engineering design.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Shesternya - The smallest of the wheels in a pair of geared wheels. Jump to navigation. If both gear wheels are approximately the same dimensions, both are called *Shesternya* (q. Gear transmission).

The angular velocity ratio is the ratio of transmission, so you can write:

$$u_{12} = \frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} = \frac{O_2P''}{O_1P''} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Gear Transmission and Angular Velocity Interaction.

In the second case, where n'' passes through the contact point, $n'' - n''$ intersects the center line R'' at the pole. In the construction state, R' does not overlap with the pole. The transmission ratio in the second case is:

$$u''_{12} = \frac{O_2P''}{O_1P''} \quad (2)$$

As seen from Figure 5.4, the ratio of incisions differs in the first and second cases, therefore:

$$u'_{12} = u''_{12} \quad (3)$$

From this, the following conclusion follows: if the angular velocity of the first gear wheel is constant (i.e., it moves in a straight line), then the angular velocity of the second wheel in the construction state will be variable, i.e., it moves unevenly. However, for most cases, this is not feasible. Machines use gear mechanisms in which the angular velocities of the gears are unchanged, i.e., gear mechanisms with a constant transmission ratio.

$$U_{12} = \text{const} \quad (4)$$

To satisfy this condition, the profile must be such that the total normal passing over the contact point must pass through a point on one centerline (R - pole) at any given time, i.e., in the condensation process, the pole R must not change its position on the centerline. Curved tooth profiles that meet such a requirement are called curved tooth profiles. Two hundred years ago, the Russian scientist Euler used this curvature to create a dental profile. Since then, cars around the world have been using gear mechanisms.

Of the above-listed parameters, one standard must be chosen, which must align with the rest. This parameter should be such that its value determines the teeth. This is often accompanied by a tooth step:

$$p = \frac{2\pi r}{z} \quad (5)$$

However, the expression for the step value includes the irrational number π , which has an infinite decimal fraction. Therefore, the step cannot be standardized. π can be standardized as part of this expression without specifying the number. This value is called the modulus m of the teeth:

$$m = \frac{2r}{z} \quad (6)$$

The modulus is defined by the tooth value, i.e., the modulus equals the height of the tooth head by the numerical value:

$$m = h_a \quad (7)$$

The module is considered a standard value and is measured in millimeters ("mm"). Therefore, all dimensions of a gear wheel are measured in millimeters. The available modules, based on the standard, assume values from half a millimeter to 100 mm. Some values of the modulus are: $m = 0.5; 1; 1.5; 2; 2.5; 3; 4; 5 \dots 100$ mm.

The geometric parameters of a gear wheel are written with formulas that relate its number of teeth, standard modulus, and standard angle $\alpha = 20^\circ$: radius of circle (8), radius of head circle $r = \frac{mz}{2}$ (9), radius of foot circle $r_f = r - 1.25m$ (10), radius of main circle $r_b = r \cdot \cos \alpha$ (11), tooth height $h = 2.25m$ (12), tooth step in a divisible circle $p = \pi \cdot m$ (13), Thread thickness (14) in a divisible circumference.

Observing these formulas, to determine all geometric dimensions of a wheel with a standard normal gear, it is enough to know two values — the number of teeth z and the modulus m .

$$S = \frac{p}{2} \quad (8)$$

This program is written for "Calculation of parameters of gear measurement," which calculates the parameters of a modular gear with a gear, parameters of a T-work gear, parameters of a screw modular transmission with a clutch module, gear parameters, parameters of a gear step transmission, parameters of a V-intstep transmission, and rack parameters.

Figure 2. Calculation of the modular gear with internal gear.

Figure 3. Table of calculation formulas for gear gauge parameters.

Gear module transmission		
Tooth height	P	$P = \pi m = \pi d / z$
Number of teeth	Z	$Z = d / m = \pi d / p$
Module agar	m	$m = p / \pi = d / z = d_a / (z + 2)$
Graduation Circle	d	$d = m z = d_a - 2m$
Additional Circle	also	$d_a = m(z - 2)$
Root Circle	df	$d_f = (d + 2.5)m$
Balance	h	$h = 2.25m$
tip height	Has	$h_a = m / \pi$
Tooth root height	hf	$h_f = 1.25m$
Center Distance	S	$S = p / 2 = \pi m / 2$
Tooth thickness	A	$a = (m z_1 - m z_2) / 2$

Figure 4. Excel Program Calculation.

Shester module transmission			π	m	d	z	z ₁	z ₂	a
			3.1415	200	100	90	80	60	40
Tooth height	P	$P = \pi m = \pi d / z$	$= D2 * E2$	$= D2 * F2 / G2$					
Number of teeth	Z	$Z = d / m = \pi d / p$	$= F2 / E2$	$= D2 * E2 / D3$					
Module if	m	$m = p / \pi = d / z = d_a / (z + 2)$	$= D3 / D2$	$= F2 / G2$	$= D7 * (G2 + 2)$				
Graduation Circle	d	$d = m z = d_a - 2m$	$= E2 * G2$	$= F2 * J2 - 2 * E2$					
In addition	d _a	$d_a = m(z + 2) = d + 2m = p(z + 2) / \pi$	$= E2 * (G2 - 2)$	$= F2 + 2 * E2$	$= D3 * (G2 + 2) / D2$				
Root circle	d _f	$d_f = d - 2.5m = m(z - 2.5) = d_a - 2h = d_a - 2h = d_a - 4.5m$	$= F2 - 2.5 * E2$	$= E2 * (G2 - 2.5)$	$= D7 - 2 * D9$	$= D7 - 2 * D9$	$= D7 - 4.5 * E2$		
Balanity	h	$h = 2.25m$	$= 2.25 * E2$						
Tip height	h _a	$h_a = m / \pi$	$= E2$	$= D3 / D2$					
The height of the tooth root	h _f	$h_f = 1.25m$	$= 1.25 * E2$						
Center distance	S	$S = p / 2 = \pi m / 2$	$= D3 / 2$	$= D2 * E2 / 2$					
Tooth thickness	A	$a = (m z_1 + m z_2) / 2 = (d_1 + d_2) / 2$	$= (E2 * H2 - E2 * I2)$	$= (D6 - E6) / 2$					

Figure 5. Excel Program Computing(Result).

Shester module transmission			π	m	d	z	z_1	z_2	a
			3.1415	200	100	90	80	60	40
Tooth height	P	$P=\pi m=\pi d/z$	628.3	3.490555556					
Number of teeth	Z	$Z=d/m=\pi d/p$	0.5	1					
Module if	m	$m=p/\pi=d/z=d_a(z+2)$	200	1.111111111	1619200				
Graduation Circle	d	$d=mz=da-2m$	18000	3600					
In addition	d_a	$d_a=m(z+2)=d+2m=p(z+2)/\pi$	17600	500	18400				
Root circle	d_f	$d_f=d-2.5m=m(z-2.5)=d_a-2h=da-2h=da-4.5m$	-400	17500	16700	16700	16700		
Balanity	h	$h=2.25m$	450						
Tip height	h_a	$h_a=m=p/\pi$	200	200					
The height of the tooth root	h_f	$h_f=1.25m$	250						
Center distance	S	$S=p/2=\pi m/2$	314.15	314.15					
Tooth thickness	A	$a=(mz_1+mz_2)/2=(d_1+d_2)/2$	4000	7200					

The program code:

```
#include<iostream>
#include<math.h>
using namespace std;
int main(){
double P1,P2,Z1,Z2,pi,m,m1,m2,m3,d,d1,d2,da;
float df,h,ha,hf,S1,S2,a;
int z,z1,z2; pi=3.1415;
cout<<"m="; cin>>m;
cout<<"z="; cin>>z; cout<<"z1="; cin>>z1;
cout<<"z2="; cin>>z2; cout<<"a="; cin>>a;
P1=pi*m; P2=pi*d/z; Z1=d/m; Z2=pi*d/P1; d1=m*z; d2=d*a-2*m; da=m*(z+2);
df=(d+2.5)*m; h=2.25*m; ha=m; ha=P1/pi; hf=1.25*m; S1=P1/2; S2=pi*m/2;
a=(m*z1-m*z2)/2;
cout<<"****N A T I J A****"<<endl;
cout<<"P1="<<P1<<endl; cout<<"P2="<<P2<<endl;
cout<<"Z1="<<Z1<<endl; cout<<"Z2="<<Z2<<endl;
cout<<"da="<<da<<endl; cout<<"df="<<df<<endl;
cout<<"ha="<<ha<<endl; cout<<"hf="<<hf<<endl;
cout<<"S1="<<S1<<endl; cout<<"S2="<<S2<<endl;
cout<<"a="<<a;
return 0;}
```

Output results:

m=60; z=80; z1=70; z2=40; a=20;
P1=1888.49; P2=8.25653e-319; Z1=3.50431e-319; Z2=3.504301-319;
Da=4920; df=150; ha=60; hf=75; S1=94.245; S2=94.245; a=900.

CONCLUSION

The parameters of the gear gauge were calculated, including those for the internal gear modular gear, screw modular transmission, clutch module, gear parameters, gear step extensions, screw step extension, and rack parameters. Depending on the specific type of production, it is possible to highlight several key areas and requirements that are common in the organization of any workplace.

These parameters play a crucial role in ensuring the efficiency and functionality of gear mechanisms across various applications, and understanding them is essential for optimizing gear system performance in different production settings.

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